

GHOEUR GULAM'S POETIC SKILLS

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Abstract. This article discusses the literary influence and artistic skills of Ghafur Ghulam, the factors that influenced his formation and improvement of his skills as a skilled novelist and short story writer.

Keywords: writer, story, image, skill, short story, world, character, artistic psychology, poetics, phenomenon, folklore.

ПОЭТИЧЕСКОЕ МАСТЕРСТВО ГОФУРА ГУЛАМА

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются литературное влияние и художественные способности Гафура Гулама, факторы, повлиявшие на его становление и совершенствование его навыков как искусного романиста и писателя коротких рассказов.

Ключевые слова: писатель, рассказ, образ, мастерство, мир, персонаж, художественная психология, поэтика, явление, фольклор.

INTRODUCTION

During the years of independence, a wide range of opportunities were created for the development of free thought, literary studies and criticism. This situation also drastically changed the attitude towards the personality and work of Gafur Ghulam. The roots and essence of his creative heritage have been penetrated more and more deeply. The analysis and interpretations were directed to the discovery of completely new aspects of the Gafur Ghulam phenomenon, unlike previous studies. The master of words, Gafur Ghulam, who studied creatively and extensively from the ideological and aesthetic traditions of folk art, served as a great school for the life and work of which folklore was of great importance. Adib studied people's life and dreams, their spiritual world, psychology, character, spirituality, aesthetic taste and artistic thinking, rich language from folklore. That's why Gafur Ghulam's comic stories and stories that make you laugh and cry and make you cry have gained popularity among the people. He was one of the writers who made an incomparable contribution to Uzbek realistic storytelling and storytelling, and he successfully worked in this field until the end of his life.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

In the personality and creative heritage of Ghafur Ghulam, one can find extremely diverse manifestations of the influence of folk art. For example:

1. In the comedy "Effendi will not die" folklore works are recreated.
2. The story "Hasan Kayfiy" is written in the style of folklore.
3. The story "Resurrected Corpse" is told based on folklore motifs and features characteristic of folk art images. Mulla Mamajon's character is typified on this basis. It is important that the people and creativity of Gafur Ghulam's prose strengthened the spirit of humor, heroism, vitality, and wisdom. Adib even based dozens of his feuilletons on the plot and form of Nasridin Efandi's anecdotes, and in this way even raised them to the level of satirical stories. Works such as "Kavush not taken to his wife", "Looks at his feet", "Tail in the plow" prove our opinion. Commenting on Gafur Ghulam's short prose, literary critic S. Mamajonov quotes the following

words of Oibek: "Gafur shows the image of people well in his stories. He knows how to get into the psychology of his minor characters. He sees their concepts, views, goals and aspirations narrowly." In fact, Gafur Ghulam used various image tools in mutual proportion to illuminate the psyche of his hero, which in his stories and stories is the "big" of the "small" hero. played an important role in describing the world. Gafur Ghulam does not shy away from life. He can show social tragedy through a family tragedy, as an example of a personal tragedy. He considers it important to focus on the heart of the hero rather than the depiction of domestic situations. In most cases, the author intervenes in the solution. Nevertheless, they contain mental images that reflect a complete determinism and brutal realism.

DISCUSSION

In a certain sense, the author's experiences in storytelling served as a unique ground for the success of his stories. Gafur Ghulam shows the spiritual world, intentions, and inner experiences of the heroes through their actions, speech, and dreams. The writer refers to their behavior when expressing the character's reaction to a particular event. Most of them are simple and poor people, and they attract our attention because they are people of honesty, conscience and religion. After all, the writer always gives a realistic basis for the plot and character conflicts. It reflects the national color taken from the Uzbek way of life. In some cases, it can turn joy into bitter laughter. His aesthetic ideal is based on deep humanity. Gafur Ghulam's prose works express the aesthetic ideal of humanitarianism, loyalty to the truth, respect for the people, compassion, and orphanhood.

RESULTS

The poems presented in Gafur Ghulam's stories are diverse in size and genre. In order to substantiate the idea presented in the story, the author selects some verses from the works of classical poets, examples from the genres of folk oral works such as lapar, yor-yor, song. In the stories, there are also poetic pieces that are the product of the writer's independent work, some of them are versions of works of individual poets, and some of them are variants of poems existing in folklore, reworked by Gafur Ghulam. In general, Gafur Ghulam's stories and stories are beautifully polished, musical melodiousness, prose expression and poetry lines, free transition from poem to prose, verses of classical poets and examples of folk art. use, sometimes a creative approach to them is important. The combination of prose and verse brought out the uniqueness of the lyric-epic prose style and ensured the poetic appeal of the genre language. In a certain sense, the author's experiences in storytelling served as a unique ground for the success of his stories.

CONCLUSIONS

In a word, when we talk about Gafur Ghulam's personality, memory and legacy, we compare this great man, first of all, as a broad, literal poet of the people, his immortal name and we bow before his eternal creation. The literary-scientific heritage of Gafur Ghulam, his social activities, his place in Uzbek literature, the linguistic features of his works, and the study of his creative products in the educational system are one of the most important issues. Studying Gafur Ghulam at the level of world literature, looking at the cosmogonic scope of his thinking leads to a deeper understanding of his place in the literary life of his time and his importance for today.

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